

KEY INDICATORS

In Denmark, 290,418 hectares (2024) constituted 11.1% of total farmland, making it one of the countries with an above-EU organic area share (EU: 11.1%). Organic farmland less than doubled from 2001 to 2024, thus showing smaller growth than most EU countries. Retail sales amounted to 2,223 million euros, and Denmark held rank two (after Switzerland) in terms of organic retail sales shares (11.6%) in the European Union and worldwide.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

168,372 ha (6.4%)

290,418 ha (11.1%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2024

72.5%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

150,031 ha (6.8%)

114,534 ha (4.8%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

240 ha (3.5%)

2,628 ha (9.2%) (2022)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

20,735 ha (5.5%)

166,417 (74.8%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

8,552 † (22.6%) (2022)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)

3,525 (6.1%)

4,095 (11%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

44 (2022)

Processors

777

983 (2022)

Importers

36

126 (2022)

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

270 M €

2,223 M€ (11.6%)

Per Capita Consumption

50.5 €

372.9 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2024

726 %

Imports

N/D

84,124 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN DENMARK

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, Eurostat, Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC SALES IN DENMARK

Source: Statistics Denmark, Organic Denmark, LF

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Denmark CAP strategic plan provides for an 80% increase in supported organic area and expenditure compared with 2018. Planned maintenance payments are similar to or slightly higher than the previous period. Conversion payments for grassland and arable crops have increased by ca. 20% and are substantially higher than maintenance payments in both periods. For fruit crops, the changes and differences are more modest. Payment rates are planned to be increased from 2024 according to the new organic action plan.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	223 kha	403 kha (+81%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	8.5%	15% (+80%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	87%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	41 M€	74 M€ (+81%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	184 €	184 €

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P1)*	254 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	819 M€	26.2%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	152 M€	5.2%
Total CAP Expenditure	4,848 M€	

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2023	P2	277/344	277/344	277/344	869/965
	2026	P1	422/509	422/509	422/509	958/1046
Change from 2023 to 2026			52%/48%	52%/48%	52%/48%	10%/8%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2023	P2	117/204	117/204	117/204	654/741
	2026	P1	181/268	181/268	181/268	717/804
Change from 2023 to 2026			55%/31%	55%/31%	55%/31%	10%/9%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2023	P2	137%/ 69%	137%/69%	137%/69%	33%/30%
	2026	P1	133%/ 90%	133%/90%	133%/90%	34%/30%

The higher rates are for low intensity production, max. 60 kgN/ha; the lower rates for higher intensity with max. 100 kgN/ha

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Denmark has the longest track record of multiple organic action plans dating back to 1995. In recent periods, the action plans have become more focused on a limited range of actions, on the basis of continuity of initiatives such as research, advice and public procurement established under previous plans. The current plan contains more information on funding of initiatives, including from CAP Strategic Plans, than is common in many action plans.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2018-21	More than the 9.2% of UAA in 2017	More than the 10.5% of retail sales in 2017
Current Action Plan	2023-30	21% of UAA by 2030	Double sales by 2030 to 25.8 billion DKK* retail, 4.6 billion DKK* catering and 5.8 billion DKK* exports

In both periods, there is a 60% organic target for state canteens under joint green food policy (equivalent to the silver level of the Danish Organic Cuisine Label)

*1 DKK = 0.13€ (18 March 2024)

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2018 - 2021)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2023 - 2030)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Denmark is almost 13%. Organic aquaculture has been supported as part of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture, including investment aids. The Strategic Plan set a target of 20% of Danish seafood production to be organic by 2020. The national OAP includes organic aquaculture as a focus for research and development. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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